

“Above All Things Let God Be Loved the Most”: Françoise d’Amboise, Duchess, Carmelite Nun, and Witness of the Devout Life

Introduction

A fifteenth century duchess, living a courtly life but being imbued by the spirit of the *devotio moderna* movement, enshrines Jesus’ prayer for his disciples in John’s Gospel to be *in* the world but not *of* the world (cf. Jn 15:19, 17:14-16). The Carmelite Bl. Françoise d’Amboise lived during a very turbulent time, with France in war and the people suffering the consequent tribulations. Despite being protected within the riches and comforts of courtly life, d’Amboise disregarded these and thought them secondary to the pleas of the poor and the needy, for whom she dedicated herself entirely. She was truly in the world, her role as Duchess of Brittany placed her in the heart of society, but her heart and spirit were elsewhere, so much so that her dying husband’s will provided her with

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the necessary means so that “[his] spouse could, with greater disposition, attend to a life of prayer, charitable acts, and devotion.”¹

Ever since she was young, d’Amboise wanted to join the religious life; alas, her social standing and, more particularly, her family prohibited it. However, by providence she met the saintly Carmelite reformer Bl. Jean Soreth (1394-1471). Together they ventured on the reform project of founding Carmelite female monasteries in France imbued by the spirituality of the *devotio moderna* movement which, by this time, had grown so much in the Low Lands that it almost immediately permeated into Germany, first, and then France. We will argue that her impact on Carmelite sisterhood in France was to become so vital that for d’Amboise’s imprint on medieval Carmelite sisterhood to be well understood, one must observe the complex development of this feminine reality within the Northern European area of the Order in light of its intricate connection to the spiritual qualities of the *devotio moderna*. As we shall see, the parallelism between the two spiritual traditions is astonishingly close not only on a historical but also on a spiritual level.

This article will commence by giving a brief biography of the duchess. Then, we will go over the historical and spiritual contexts within which the Carmelite nuns in France were founded as part of Soreth’s reform project. Then, constituting the central focus of this study and in order to truly appreciate the spiritual heritage of the duchess, we will have a close look at her *Exhortations* in which clear connections are observed with the spirituality of the *devotio moderna*. Finally, a word of conclusion and synthesis seeks to tie up loose ends.

From a Royal Life at Court to a Carmelite Nun ²

Françoise d’Amboise was born at the *chateau* of Thouars on 28 September 1427 to Louis d’Amboise, Viscount of Thouars, and Marie de Rieux, Baroness of Encenis. Firstborn of the noble couple, at the age of four she was betrothed

¹ “Profilo storico-biografico,” in *Esortazioni della Beata Francesca d’Amboise*, ed. Carmelo S. Anna (Anagni: Tipografia Achille, 1996), 10 (hereafter, *Esortazioni*, ed. Carmelo S. Anna).

² Largely based on Vital Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise,” *Carmelus* 11, no. 2 (1964): 223-229; Joachim Smet, “Bl. Frances of Amboise (1427-1485),” in *The Carmelites: A History of the Brothers of Our Lady of Mt Carmel* (Rome: Institutum Carmelitarum, 1975), 1:109-13; Claudio Catena, “Francesca d’Amboise, beata,” in *Santi del Carmelo: Biografie da vari dizionari*, ed. Ludovico Saggi, intr. Valentino Macca (Rome: Institutum Carmelitarum, 1972), 211-212; Giovanni Grosso, “Francesca d’Amboise, beata (1427-1485),” in *Dizionario Carmelitano*, eds., Emanuele Boaga and Luigi Borriello (Rome: Città Nuova, 2008), 384-385.

to thirteen-year-old Peter, the second son of John V, Duke of Brittany, whom she then married in 1442 at the age of fifteen. With her mother fleeing Thouars to the protection of Arthur de Richemont, brother of the Duke of Brittany,³ d'Amboise was brought up under the care of the Duchess of Brittany, Jeanne de France, who is described as a devout woman and who shaped d'Amboise's pious character. As a matter of fact, we are told that since an early age, despite being engaged, d'Amboise wished to be consecrated to God in religious life. We are told that she showed great compassion and predilection for the poor alongside a great devotion to the blessed Mother of God, under whose protection she placed herself and which she will later pass on in her monastic foundations.

After their father's death, having his elder brother Francis I also died suddenly, Peter succeeded them as the Duke of Brittany in 1450, taking on the name of Peter II. Becoming known as “the simple,” Peter was not one of the greater dukes of Brittany; he was weak, rough, impulsive, and easily manipulated, but not nevertheless an unlovable type. Being ill-treated by her husband, d'Amboise was discontented in marriage. Still, she took seriously the call to Christian life, and embodied the principle of being *in* the world but not *of* the world. She dedicated herself to charitable work with the poor and the sick, becoming also a great benefactor of the female Dominican and Franciscan monasteries in Nantes, founded a hospice for lepers, and even managed to convert her husband from his ill manners. She also put her spiritual and psychological abilities to the service of the duchy, especially as her husband was not only timid, but prone to jealousy, stubborn, and violent. The good governance of the duchy has been credited to her due to the good counsels she gave her husband and her total dedication to the common good.⁴ Duke Francis II, her husband's successor as Duke of Brittany, testified that d'Amboise “always concerned herself with the public good and the

³ After the liberation of Orléans, where Louis d'Amboise was in the following of Jeanne d'Arc, *la Pucelle*, he was charged of treason against King Charles VII due to a disaccord with Georges de La Tremoille, who was favoured by the King. At first, Louis was condemned to death, but the King pardoned him and instead chose to confiscate the Chateau d'Amboise from d'Amboise's father. Still a child, d'Amboise was taken to safety with her mother to the Court of Brittany in Vannes and Nantes. Because of the family's financial ruin, d'Amboise's father signed a contract of marriage for his daughter on 21 July 1431 with the Duke of Brittany. See: Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Françoise d'Amboise,” 223.

⁴ See: Gui Alexis Lobineau, *Histoire de Bretagne, composée sur les titres et les auteurs originaux* (Paris: Michel Guignard, 1707), 1:678; “Fondation faite par le duc François II en faveur du couvent des Trois-Maries du Bon-Don (9 avril 1469),” in L'Abbé Richard, *Vie de la Bienheureuse Françoise d'Amboise, Duchesse de Bretagne et Religieuse Carmélite* (Nantes-Paris: V. Forest et É. Grimaud and Jacques Lecoffre, 1865), 2:315-316.

preservation of the unity of our country and duchy.” At his deathbed in 1457, her husband also testified to “the long association and companionship in marriage” pointing out the duchess’ “good and agreeable services of great obedience and humility she has shown us in health and sickness.” Bearing him no children, Peter described his wife as his “very dear and beloved sister and companion spouse,” and, at least according to certain biographers, he eventually came to respect her vow of virginity, even though he was many a time taken in by his court’s rumours of her unfaithfulness in marriage.

After her husband’s death, as she became resolved not to marry again (thereby upsetting the dynastic plans for her of her father and King Louis XI), she continued to live at the *chateau* of Nantes in a life of prayer and charity, devoting herself to help the poor in prisons, hospices, and monasteries. As her reputation for piety grew, she wanted to join the Poor Clares that she and her husband had founded in Nantes, but her health failed her.

In November 1459, she then met the saintly Carmelite Prior General Jean Soreth who was in France working on the institution of the Carmelite nuns as part of his programme of reform of the Order. Together they later founded female Carmelite monasteries in Bon-Don (1464), near Vannes, where d’Amboise would eventually join the Order in 1468, and in Les Couëts (1477), near Nantes.⁵ Further monasteries would continue to be founded after d’Amboise’s death in her spirit. For this reason, her foundations in France, with Soreth’s help of course, won her the title of the foundress of the Carmelite sisterhood in France.⁶ Her *Constitutions* came to influence not only the Carmelite nuns in Brittany but also others throughout Europe, especially with regards to frequent communion and the strict imposition of the cloistered life in order to safeguard the community’s independence from the intrusions of the rich noble gentry.⁷ She died in odour of

⁵ See, Ludovico Saggi, “Soreth Giovanni, beato,” in *Santi del Carmelo*, 324-325.

⁶ See, Titus Brandsma, “Carmes (Spiritualité de l’Ordre des): En dehors de la réforme de Sainte Thérèse,” in *Dictionnaire de spiritualité ascétique et mystique*, eds., Charles Baumgartner et alii (Paris: Beauchesne, 1953), 2:168 (hereafter, *Dictionnaire de spiritualité*); Titus Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites: 1 – Before the Reform of St Teresa and Some Developments of the Calced Tradition Thereafter,” trans. Redemptus Valabek, in *Collected Works of Titus Brandsma*, 1/Mysticism in Action, eds., Elisabeth Hense and Joseph Chalmers (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2021), 190 (hereafter, *Mysticism in Action*); See also, Peter-Thomas Rohrbach, *Journey to Carith: The Sources and Story of the Discalced Carmelites* (Washington, D.C.: ICS Publications, 2015), 126-129.

⁷ The Carmelite community of Les Couëts was renowned for its observance and fervour so much so that the foundation was rapidly being imitated in all of Europe in the foundations of new Carmelite communities. According to Yves Durand, basing his argument on Joachim Smet

sanctity in the Carmelite monastery of Les Couëts on 4 November 1485, having joined the Order seventeen years before. She was beatified by Pope Pius IX on 16 July 1863.

The Carmelite Nuns and the *devotio moderna* Movement

D’Amboise’s story brings together the spiritual élan of the times, particularly the new ‘modern’ way ushered in by the self-proclaimed *devotio moderna* movement, and the emerging female reality of the Carmelite Order.

The devotio moderna Movement in France

At the end of the fourteenth and beginning of the fifteenth centuries, the *devotio moderna* emerged in an ecclesial context of extreme exteriorisation and intellectualization of faith where “one adhered to outward appearances which substituted for the inward veneration of God.”⁸ Dissatisfied with an overall lack of observance and lax lifestyle in the Church, the devout (understood here as the members of the *devotio moderna* movement) developed an individual-centred spiritual experience emphasising interiority, personal conversion, and devotion.⁹ For this reason, the devout introduced a greater emphasis on endurance in temptations and virtues (above all, humility, obedience, and

and Etienne Catta, it is possible that Teresa of Avila had in mind the community of Les Couëts when she alludes to a “monastery in the north” where one could find the true spirit of the Order. Yves Durand, *Un Couvent dans la Ville: Les Grands Carmes de Nantes (1318-1790, 1994)*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana 23 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 1997), 98.

⁸ Titus Brandsma, “The Idea of God,” in *Mysticism in Action*, 104.

⁹ Around the same time, within Carmelite circles in Italy Bl. John Baptist of Mantua decried the state of the Church and religious life, calling for similar values of interior reform and conversion. See: Baptista Spagnoli, “Eclogae. IX. Falco. De moribus curiae romanae,” in *Poeti latini del Quattrocento*, eds., Francesco Arnaldi et alii (Milan-Napoli: Ricciardi, 1964), 898-911. Other important texts by the great Mantuan reformer are his treatises *De vita beata dialogus* and *De patientia*, which was a text born out of the spiritual-literary circle of Carlo Antonio Fantuzzi and was intended to bring spiritual solace to devout people, similar to the *Imitatio Christi* and the *Epistolarum ineditarum*. Claudio Catena sees parallelisms between the Mantuan’s *De patientia*, Thomas à Kempis’ *Imitatio Christi* and Jean Mombaer in expressions like: “male clausa sunt claustra” in line with the *devotio moderna*. Catena, *Le Carmelitane: Storia e Spiritualità*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana 9 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1969), 366, 413. Other possible parallelisms can be drawn between Gerard Groote’s *On Patience* and the Mantuan’s *On Sacred Scripture*. Compare: I. Baptistae Mantuani, *Poëtae et oratoris clarissimi operum*, 4/Soluta Oratione (Antuerpiae: Ioannem Bellerum, 1576), vol. 4, lib. 3, c. 32, fol. 170r-171r and *Devotio Moderna: Basic Writings*, The Classics of Western Spirituality Series, trans. and intro. John van Engen (New York: Paulist Press, 1988), 84-91.

renunciation of worldly careers and possessions), methodical prayer, spiritual reading, and personal reflection on the mysteries of Christ as key elements in the development of one's spiritual life. By their dedication to an inherently lay witness to the Christian values, with their overall orientation being largely practical, in the face of quite harsh opposition by seculars and religious alike, the Brothers and Sisters of the Common Life, heralds of the *devotio moderna* movement, embodied a spiritual experience that initially cast them out to the periphery of the Church. But as time passed by, and the spiritual values were brought into the more canonically accepted Congregation of Windesheim (founded in 1387 by Florens Radewijns),¹⁰ its appeal grew stronger and this lay spiritual lifestyle became increasingly popular, with the devout's spirituality quickly spreading throughout the Netherlands, Germany, Flanders, and beyond. This growth coincided also with a major movement of reform within the Religious Orders.¹¹

French spirituality of the fifteenth century was imbued by the *devotio moderna* not only principally through the works of Jean Standonck (1453-1504) and Jean Mombaer (1460-1501) but also initially through the presence of numerous Dutch students studying in Paris who had come from the schools of the Brothers of the Common Life.¹² Building on an already favourable air of reform and appeal to interiority in Paris, heralded earlier by Pierre d'Ailly (1350-1420), Jean Gerson (1363-1429), and Robert Ciboule (1403-58), these "secular masters" discarded sterile intellectualism, and, in their quest for a return to God through an authentic interior life, drew from the Fathers of the Church, the great monastic authors, and the scholastic tradition.¹³ Most importantly, although the first translation of the *Imitatio Christi* appeared in Paris in 1447, Vital Wilderink suggests that one can suppose that copies of the book in the original language

¹⁰ See, Heiko A. Oberman, "The 'Devotio Moderna' and the New Piety between the Later Middle Ages and the Early Modern Era," in *Religious Life between Jerusalem, the Desert and the World: Selected Essays by Kaspar Elm*, Studies in the History of Christian Traditions Series 180, trans. James D. Mixson (Leiden: Brill, 2016), 318.

¹¹ See, Mathilde van Dijk, "The Devotio Moderna, the Emotions and the Search for 'Dutchness,'" *BMGN - Low Countries Historical Review* 129, no. 2 (2014): 28. For a more detailed historical-spiritual analysis of the *devotio moderna* movement, see, John van Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life: Devotio Moderna and the World of the Later Middle Ages* (Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2008).

¹² See: R.R. Post, *The Modern Devotion: Confrontation with Reformation and Humanism* (Leiden: Brill, 1968), 7-8.

¹³ See, François Vandenbroucke, *Storia della spiritualità: La spiritualità del medioevo (XII-XVI secolo), nuovi ambienti e problemi*, ed. Réginald Grégoire and Giovanna della Croce (Bologna: EDB, 1991), 355.

or at least its ideas and spiritual values must have been brought over to Paris by the students of the *devotio moderna* long before, perhaps as early as 1420-4 when it is thought to have been composed in Kempen.¹⁴ Moreover, reading devotional books became commonplace also among the nobility and Christian royals of France. For instance, from the inventory of Queen Charlotte de Savoie it emerges that her collection of books at the Chateau d'Amboise included books of hours, lives of the saints, and the *Legenda Aurea* of Iacobus de Voragine. Also, King Louis XI, who pressured d'Amboise into marrying him after the death of her husband, had, among other books in his personal library, the devotional texts *De honesta voluptate* and the *Trésor de la Sapiencie* by Jean Gerson¹⁵ who was the inspirational figure behind the *devotio moderna* movement and its founder.¹⁶ The spirit of the *devotio moderna*, then, was definitely very much alive in France in d'Amboise's time.

Carmelite nuns in France

According to Joachim Smet, the first women started being affiliated in various degrees to the Carmelite Order as early as 1284, becoming known as *conversae*, *manumissae*, *pinzochere*, *beatas*, etc. The earliest recorded profession or act of oblation by one of such women was done in Bologna by Benvenuta Ranieni in 1304.¹⁷ Others followed suit in Florence and other parts of Europe, not least in France where, for instance, Jeanne de Toulouse (14th cent.) likewise lived in the spirit of the Carmelite Rule as a recluse near the Carmelite church of Toulouse. Around the same time, we are also told of a community of beguines in Cologne being affiliated to the Order in 1304, and another following suit in 1327.¹⁸ Such secular affiliations to the Order of female communities became commonplace in the Low Lands, Germany, France, the Iberian Peninsula, England, Italy and Northern Europe, albeit not in any way uniformly and regularly. Beguinages, in which these female communities lived, were houses “for devout women, servants

¹⁴ Vital Wilderink, *Les constitutions des premières carmelites en France*, Vacare Deo 2 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitarum, 1966) 121-122.

¹⁵ Lucie Gaugain, “Livres et librairie au Château d'Amboise à la fin du siècle: Entre Moyen Âge et Renaissance,” in *Lire, danser et chanter au château: La culture châtelaine, XIII^e - XVII^e siècles*, ed. Jean-Marie Cauchies et alii (Turnhout: Brepols, 2017), 93-94.

¹⁶ Ylena Mazour-Matusevich, “Gerson's legacy,” in *A Companion to Jean Gerson*, ed. Brian Patrick McGuire (Leiden: Brill, 2006), 371.

¹⁷ Smet, *The Carmelites*, 1:103.

¹⁸ Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 90.

of God, in secular habit,¹⁹ that eventually developed into religious houses (following the papal bull of 1452) in which, professing the Carmelite Rule, they received the full habit of the Carmelite Order as nuns. Being “the spirit of faith and love”²⁰ indeed strong not only in the Low Lands but elsewhere as well, Titus Brandsma ties the establishment of Carmelite nuns with the wider context of the phenomenon of women living in common without a particular Rule. He writes:

A circumstance which favoured the establishment of the Carmelite nuns was the legation and canonical visitation of Cardinal Nicholas of Cusa in Germany and the Lowlands (1451) in which he decreed that the devout women living in common in several cities but without a definite rule, e.g., the Sisters of the Common Life, should choose an approved rule and unite themselves to an existing Order. A group of women who were under the direction of the Carmelites of Gelderen and living near their church, asked for affiliation to the Order of Our Lady of Mount Carmel.²¹ This was the occasion for the Prior General to ask [Pope] Nicholas V for permission to establish a Second Order of women with the First Order of friars.²²

Permission for such regularisation was granted by the pope in 1452 through the bull *Cum Nulla*, which marks the beginning of a more systematic manner of female affiliation to the Order.²³

In France, in 1464 d’Amboise founded the first monastery for Carmelite nuns in Bon-Don, which she named in honour of the *Three Marys*. There had already been a community of Carmelite friars there (which her father-in-law Duke John V had founded in 1425) who had welcomed Soreth’s reform programme. On 16

¹⁹ “[...] pro devotis personis feminei sexus Deo famulantibus in habitu tamen saeculari.” J. Milendunck, *Chronicon universale*, f. 34r, as quoted in Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 90. At this stage, it is far too early to speak of these women as religious or regulars.

²⁰ Titus Brandsma, “Flowers of our Spiritual Heritage,” in *Mysticism in Action*, 77.

²¹ Soreth, in fact, received the beguines of Ten Elsen in Gelderen into the Order on 10 May 1452. Three months later, in Florence, several women who had been clothed in the white mantle in August 1450 were likewise received into the Order. That same year, finally regularising the reception of women into the Carmelite Order, Pope Nicholas V’s bull *Cum Nulla*, decreed on 7 October 1452, bestowed papal authorisation on the Prior General for receiving women into the Carmelite Order both as “religious” and “secular” and is, therefore, considered to inaugurate the institution of Carmelite sisterhood. See, Smet, *The Carmelites*, 1:105. The first Carmelite monastery in Gelderen was on Veerter Street. About three other monasteries in Gelderen and Nieuwerk were founded, which became significant for the history of the Order. M. Josefina Ther, *Geldrischer Heimatkalender* (Geldern: n.d., 1975), 114-119.

²² Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 191.

²³ Catena contests that Soreth is, in fact, through the acquisition of this papal bull, the founder of Carmelite sisterhood, insisting that the bull was given to the Carmelites of Florence. See: Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, lxii-lxiv.

February 1460, d’Amboise obtained the permission of Pope Pius II to construct a monastery for nuns next to the Carmelite church of Bon-Don. The papal bull established the Carmelite community as a religious one, meaning that it was tied by the strict observance of the Carmelite Rule as well as the vow of the cloistered life under pain of excommunication *ipso facto* should anyone be found to be inobservant of it. Emphasis was especially made on the vows of poverty and obedience. The community was also to count no more than twenty-two nuns. Soreth sent some nuns from the monastery of Liège (Flanders), founded in 1457, also named in honour of the *Three Marys*,²⁴ to instruct the new community in the Carmelite life. These were received by d’Amboise at Vannes at first in her *chateau* before transferring to the monastery once it was finished some months later. Jeanne d’Avayne was elected the first prioress. Later foundations followed in the following years in similar fashion.²⁵

Four years later, fulfilling her lifelong desire to consecrate herself to God, d’Amboise joined the community of Bon-Don on 25 March 1468, receiving the Carmelite habit from Soreth himself. After much opposition from her family and from her brother-in-law Duke Francis II who pressured her to remarry, took away her dowry, even prohibited her entry in religious life as well as the foundation of the monastery,²⁶ the once “Princesse Dame Françoisse d’Amboise, Duchesse de Bretagne, Comtesse de Montfort et de Benon,” rubbing shoulders with the noble dukes, princes and even the King of France himself, became the “humble servant

²⁴ One must keep in mind that numerous female foundations were made in The Netherlands, Flanders, Germany, and France which derived from the Carmelite monastery of Liège. This fact not only shows that Soreth bestowed considerable time and effort in this monastery but also that Liège became a spiritual centre of Carmelite sisterhood in Northern Europe. The nuns were placed under Soreth himself, who frequently returned to Liège after his trips around Europe. The bishop of Liège praised the nuns for their “life, morals, and conversation in the Lord.” They were of strict observance, had no personal property or rents, recited the canonical hours, and observed perpetual enclosure. They also took in young girls as scholars, to whom they gave instruction and from among whom they recruited novices. In 1575, they erected a separate boarding school which flourished until the French Revolution. See, Smet, *The Carmelites*, 1:106-109; Adrianus Staring, “The Carmelite Sisters in The Netherlands: Liège 1457,” *Carmelus* 10, no. 1 (1963): 62-65.

²⁵ See, Giovanni Grosso, *Il B. Jean Soreth (1394-1471): Priore Generale, Riformatore, e Maestro Spirituale dell’Ordine Carmelitano* (S.Th.D. thesis, Pontificia Università Gregoriana, 2007), 233-238.

²⁶ To this opposition she replied by publicly professing aloud her vow of perpetual chastity during mass before communion. Peter-Thomas Rohrbach, *Journey to Carith: The Story of the Carmelite Order*, 3rd ed. (Washington, D.C.: ICS, 2015), 130.

of Jesus Christ.”²⁷ Against her will, in 1471 d’Amboise was elected prioress of Bon-Don and continued to oversee the community even after she was transferred to the new community of Les Couëts in 1480. Humility is foundational in her spiritual worldview. She accepts the office of prioress only under obedience to Soreth. On her deathbed she asks forgiveness for her many faults to both the vicar and the prioress of the community as a true humble servant of the crucified Christ.²⁸ It is not a coincidence, then, that iconographically *notre mère la sainte duchesse*, as she is still known today, is always portrayed in contemplation of the crucifix. Already in the fifteenth century, Bouduin Laërse noted that in joining religious life “she embraced humility [...] and devoted herself to all practices of perfection.”²⁹

Imbued by the Spirit of the devotio moderna

Brandsma asserts that “there is a direct relationship between the reform of Bl. John Soreth who lived ordinarily at Liège and who was an intimate friend of the Duke of Burgundy, and of the propagators of the *devotio moderna* in the Lowlands.”³⁰ Like the devout, Soreth popularised methodical prayer, regular meditation, and mental prayer as an effective means of dissemination among the many as it was accessible to everyone through its use of imagination and the sensible memory.³¹ This is to be considered something new within the Order

²⁷ Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise,” 227-228.

²⁸ Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise,” 229.

²⁹ Bouduin Laërse, *Collections d’exemples*, as quoted in Richard, *Vie de la bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise*, 2:14.

³⁰ Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 187. The Brethren of the Common Life founded and directed schools, among others, in Liège. See, Paul Mestwerdt et alii, *Die Anfänge des Erasmus: Humanismus und Devotio Moderna*, Studien zur Kultur und Geschichte der Reformation 2 (Leipzig: R. Haupt, 1917), 139-140. Gerard Groote himself (considered to be the founder of the *devotio moderna* movement) had visited Liège. See, Post, *The Modern Devotion*, 138.

³¹ The influence of the *devotio moderna* was also to be found in Italy and is noticeable in the *Constitutions* of the monastery of Parma which prescribed meditation in common twice a day. Such prescription passed on to the monastery of Ferrara, then to Florence. The practice of meditation was linked also to the celebration of the liturgy as an interiorised prolongation of communal prayer. Terms like ‘contemplation’ and ‘devotion’ were used to indicate the practice of meditation, which was understood as a means of purification. Resonating with the language of the *Imitatio Christi*, Maddalena de’ Pazzi uses the image of an effusion of rain dew for meditation which irrigates the heart disposing it for perfection. See: Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 364; Claudio Catena, “Antiquae Constitutiones Monialium Carmelitarum,” *Analecta Ordinis Carmelitarum* 17 (1952): 203, 210, 237.

and reflects the preference for mental prayer by the devout for its formative value over vocal prayer, as it gives more space to interiorisation.³² Commenting on Soreth as the greatest propagator of this new ‘modern’ way in Carmelite spirituality, Brandsma continues:

His *Expositio paraenetica in regulam carmelitarum*, written in 1455 and entirely animated with the ancient spirit, adapts the life of the Order to the new circumstances. A Frenchman, he underwent the influence of the Victorines and Saint Bernard; but, from all evidence, he was won over to the *devotio moderna* and to systematic meditation. For him meditation has a three-fold object: 1) the book of nature in which God teaches us so many mysteries and which we should admire because it reveals God’s law to us, the ordinary subject of the Carmelite’s consideration according to the Rule; 2) the book of Holy Scripture which must be constantly read because it was written for us and contains the law of God; 3) the book of life which God writes for each of us and which will teach us how we should observe God’s law. Thus, there are three distinct forms of meditation which can, however; be combined. In the exposition of the Rule, the insistence on the practice of virtue and the exercise of meditation is remarkable.³³

Gradually, mainly in female Carmelite monasteries, the practice of meditation was detached from the moments of liturgical celebrations. Basing himself on the observations of Jean Chatillon and Pierre Debongnie on the *devotio moderna*, Claudio Catena notes that having meditation in Carmel as a communal activity following the liturgy had the same intention of the devout to interiorise liturgical prayer.³⁴ Also, like the devout, Carmelite nuns made use of pious texts like the *Omeliario quadragesimale* and the *Psalterio davitico* to sustain the meditative interiorisation of the liturgy. Hence, Catena concludes that while for the Flemish devout the ideal to contemplate was Christ as revealed in the Scriptures, for the Carmelite nuns the same ideal was contemplated within the context of the liturgy.³⁵

³² As an interpreter of the Pope Eugene IV’s mitigation of the Carmelite Rule in 1432, Soreth’s reformed Constitutions highly recommend prayer, meditative recollection, and contemplation. This coincided with the expansion of the *devotio moderna* movement which was actively engaged in promoting meditation and mental prayer to the lay faithful. Durand, *Un Couvent dans la Ville*, 57. See also: Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 363; Jean Chatillon, “Devotio,” in *Dictionnaire de spiritualité*, 3:714.

³³ Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 187-189.

³⁴ See, Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 365.

³⁵ Ibid.

Also, the Marian dimension of Carmel fitted perfectly and harmoniously “with the chief spiritual themes of the *devotio moderna*, namely, imitation of Christ and meditation on the life and passion of our Saviour.”³⁶ For example, Bl. Arcangela Giralani (1460-94) is said to have contemplated the passion of Christ to such an extent that she seemed to be out of her senses while meditating. A similar anecdote is said of Bl. Giovanna Scopelli (1439-91).³⁷ Also, in line with the piety of the devout, Carmelites were propagators of devotional literature to assist meditation on the mysteries of the life of Christ. Worthy of mention, for instance, is the sixteenth century classic *The Spiritual Pilgrimage to the Holy Land* published by Jan Pascha in 1563, which is a meditation book and a precursor of the *via crucis* as we know it today. Another Carmelite text produced earlier in the fifteenth century was John of Hildesheim’s *Historia trium regum*, which contributed to the propagation of the devotion to the mysteries of the infancy of Jesus.³⁸ Other forms of devotion which resonated with the Carmelite nuns were that of St Joseph and the Guardian Angel.³⁹

The call of the *devotio moderna* to interiority as the underlying principle of one’s daily activity resonated with the Carmelite spirit. One adhered to God in the interior life both in established times of prayer, meditation, work, and study, as well as in active apostolate. Catena notes that even though Carmelites “did not expressly adhere to the *devotio moderna*, however they always lived up to it with great freedom of spirit, without desiring nor excluding a proper call to interiority coming from God.”⁴⁰ This ideal was intensely lived primarily by the nuns within the Order who lived a deep life of solitude and prayer.⁴¹ Brandsma notices that developments inspired by the *devotio moderna*, were a new way of living the precept of the Rule which calls on Carmelites to “meditate day and night on the law of the Lord and to watch in prayer” (n. 10). He comments, “For thus apostolic activity is subordinated to the primary end of the Order which is conversation with God. And so providentially exterior activity proceeds from union with God but should not interrupt it.”⁴² Finally, the treatises of Denis the

³⁶ Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 187. Brandsma also mentions the propagation of the devotion to the immediate family members of Mary, namely, St Joseph, St Anne and St Joachim.

³⁷ Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 369.

³⁸ See, Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 187.

³⁹ See, Catena, *Le Carmelitane*, 390.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 407.

⁴¹ See *ibid.*, 408.

⁴² Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 187-189. Brandsma, however, points also to a noticeable difference in the way Soreth understood the spiritual and mystical life as he writes,

Carthusian on the spiritual life were influential both to Carmelite nuns and the *devotio moderna*. Being the mysticism of the Chartreuse and Jan van Ruusbroec dear to both spiritual currents, together with a love of solitude, contemplation and an aspiration to a stricter observance, meant that “the contact between the Carmelite nuns, their spiritual fathers, and the masters of the *devotio moderna* was not merely occasional; it was a matter more of a common spirit.”⁴³

The *Exhortations*, a Window into d’Amboise’s Devout Soul

A Historical Overview

In 1621, the Carmelite Christophe Le Roy published in Paris *Les saintes ardeurs de la Mère Françoise d’Amboise*. These are meditations, attributed to d’Amboise, on the seven last words of Christ on the cross and on the Virgin Mary. However, Wilderink is convinced this attribution is wrong as the text is too “pompous.” Notwithstanding, the publication does include the first known biography of the duchess, which is later developed by Léon de Saint-Jean in 1634 and Albert Le Grand in 1637. In the twenty-sixth chapter, Léon de Saint-Jean includes also the first reference to the *Exhortations*, albeit in summary form composed by himself.⁴⁴ Albert Le Grand then copies and elaborates Léon’s biography as well as his *summarium* of the *Exhortations*, which is here divided into thirty-nine short axioms in the thirty-fourth chapter of d’Amboise’s *Vie*.⁴⁵ In 1653, Sebastien des Anges, a Carmelite of the Reform of Touraine, publishes eighteen “sentences et maximes” by d’Amboise in a *raparium* collection dedicated to Duchess Henriette de la Guiche of Angoulesme.⁴⁶ In 1680, des

“What is perhaps more astonishing is the fact that this follower of the Devotio Moderna spoke so remarkably of the vision of God and of mystical graces about which the authors of this school are in general very reserved.”

⁴³ Ibid., 191.

⁴⁴ Fr. L. [Léon de Saint-Jean], *La vie de la tres-illustre et vertueuse Françoise d’Amboise, iadis Duchesse de Bretagne, et Religieuse de l’Ordre de la Glorieuse Vierge Marie du Mont-Carmel* (Paris: Joseph Cottureau, 1634), 187-196.

⁴⁵ Albert Le Grand, “La vie de la Bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise, Duchesse de Bretagne, Fondatrice des Carmelites audit pays,” in *La vie, gestes, mort, et miracles des saints de la Bretagne armorique* (Rennes: Jean Vayar et Julian Ferre, 1659), 445-448.

⁴⁶ “Sentences et maximes de la B. Duchesse de Bretagne Françoise d’Amboise qui se fist Carmelite l’an 1467, trois ans apres qu’elle eust fondé les Religieuses Carmelites en Bretagne,” in Sebastien des Anges, *Maximes et sentences spirituelles tirees des oeuvres et de la vie des saints pour servir aux ames qui aspirent à la perfection* (Paris: Sebastien Hure, 1653), 149-154.

Anges' companion in the Reform of Touraine, Daniel of the Virgin Mary, translates Albert Le Grand's biography into Latin and publishes these extracts in the *Speculum Carmelitanum*.⁴⁷ While further elaborating d'Amboise's biography, in the nineteenth century Abbé Richard and Viscount Edouard Sioc'han de Kersabiec follow suit in publishing these extracts as "maximes,"⁴⁸ and by 1892 these are translated into Spanish and published in Barcelona by the Jesuit J. A. Solazzi.⁴⁹ In the twentieth century, Wilderink then discovers the *Exhortations* in the Archives départementales d'Ille-et-Vilaine (Rennes) which contain valuable manuscripts from the nearby Carmelite monastery of Rennes that was suppressed in 1792.⁵⁰ Although we do not know exactly where Léon de Saint-Jean was able to read the manuscript of the *Exhortations*, whether it was in Vannes (Bon-Don) or Les Couëts, Wilderink finds that Léon's extracts published in the seventeenth century correspond perfectly to the manuscript he discovered. He finds that the Rennes manuscript is a copy of a text once conserved in the Carmelite monastery of Vannes, which was founded in 1622.⁵¹ Convinced of their authenticity, he then publishes the fuller text of the *Exhortations* in 1964.⁵² Pointing out further that such a text must have always existed, he refers to a letter, currently preserved in the Carmelite General Archive of Rome, that the community of Vannes sent to Emilio Jacomelli, the Vicar General of the Order, in February

⁴⁷ "Vita B. Franciscæ Amboisæ, Virginis in Matrimonio, ex Ducissa Britannia, Monialis, Monialium Ordinis B. Virginis Mariæ de Monte Carmeli in Britannia Armorica Fundatricis," Daniele a Virgine Maria, *Speculum Carmelitanum sive Historia Eliani Ordinis Fratrum Beatissimæ Virginis Mariæ de Monte Carmelo* (Antuerpiae: Tip. Michaelis Knobbari, 1680), 2:740-752.

⁴⁸ L'Abbé Richard, *Vie de la Bienheureuse Françoise d'Amboise*, 2 vols. (see n. 3, *supra*), translated in L'Abbate Richard, *Compendio della vita della Beata Francesca d'Amboise, Duchessa di Bretagna e Religiosa Carmelitana*, trans. Santi Mattei (Roma: Tipi del Salviucci, 1869); V.^{ic} E. Sioc'han de Kersabiec, *La Bienheureuse Françoise d'Amboise, Duchesse de Bretagne* (Nantes-Paris: V. Forest et É. Grimaud and Ambroise Prey, 1865).

⁴⁹ "Máximas espirituales de la Beata Francisca de Amboise," in *Avisos espirituales de Santa Maria Magdalena de Pazzi, religiosa carmelita calzada: Van añadidas algunas 'Advertencias' de Santa Teresa y las 'Máximas' de la Beata Francisca de Amboise, duquesa de Bretaña*, ed. J. A. Solazzi, trans. D. Aureliano Estany (Barcelona: Tipografía Católica, 1892), 125-134.

⁵⁰ The version of the *Exhortations* we have in hand today, and which is being used for this study, hails from this discovery. See, Carmélites du Saint-Sépulcre à Rennes, *Règles, statuts et ordonnances*, 27 H 3, 171-229.

⁵¹ This complete history is given in Wilderink, "Les 'Exhortations' de la Bienheureuse Françoise d'Amboise," 221-223.

⁵² [Françoise d'Amboise], "Exortations et ordonnances faites et dictes de nostre révérande et très sainte Mère la Duchesse en ces chapitres et aux receptions des novice [sic]," *Carmelus* 11, no. 2 (1964): 239-266 (hereafter, *Exhortations*).

1679 which mentions not only d’Amboise’s “rare example of virtue” but also her “saintly admonitions which she has left us for the nourishment of our soul.”⁵³ More importantly, in 1966 he then establishes a direct influence of the *devotio moderna*, specifically the *Imitatio Christi*, on d’Amboise’s *Exhortations* and, therefore, her spirituality.⁵⁴

First Impressions of the Text

Even with the fuller version in hand, the *Exhortations* rather resemble fragmentary extracts or notes, more than a formal treatise. Nonetheless, the fact that the manuscript was found containing also a handwritten copy of the Carmelite Rule, the revised Constitutions of the Breton Carmelite nuns, and the ordinances of the Carmelite Generals Enrico Silvio and Giovanni Antonio Filippini, indicates that the text was considered in high regard by the community. Wilderink suggests that the *Exhortations* might have been pronounced by d’Amboise when she was the prioress of Les Couëts as the text contains occasional complaints that she has been in office for too long. For this reason, the *Exhortations* might have been pronounced and written sometime after 1480. This means that the *Exhortations* present d’Amboise as full of life’s wisdom which she imparts most tenderly but resolutely to her sisters.

The style of the *Exhortations* is direct as the text we have in hand was primarily a series of brief orations which the prioress addressed (and still does) every day to her community normally in choir or in the chapter hall. It is believed that a sister subsequently wrote down what she could remember. We do not know when these annotations were written, but the sister’s use of the first-person singular shows her literary intention quite clearly. Not only did she intend to compile Mother d’Amboise’s counsels and spiritual thoughts, but also to conserve the direct witness of their foundress and prioress. It is most probable that she would have written down these notes in the silence of her cell, after chapter, or even after some days. This might explain why ideas are explained briefly, never quite fully developed, they lack logical coherence, and the twenty-two chapters have wide-ranging scopes, which means that the *Exhortations* are merely a window into d’Amboise’s soul and not a complete manifestation of her spiritual journey. Indeed, were one to neglect this literary fact, one would expect more spiritual depth from the duchess, seeing the extent she went through to join the religious

⁵³ Archivum Generale Ordinis Carmelitarum, II Turonia 4, as quoted in Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Françoise d’Amboise,” 223.

⁵⁴ See, Wilderink, *Les constitutions des premières carmelites en France*, 178-187.

life. Nevertheless, the fact that these mystical elements – especially, the cross of Christ, silence, and humility – are lightly brushed upon in the text but worded most beautifully, notwithstanding the limitations of seeing d’Amboise through the medium of her writer, shows how outstanding her spirit was.

D’Amboise’s exhortations – at least in the collection we have in hand, as we can be fairly certain that there are more which have not been annotated or have been lost – are essentially brief commentaries on the Carmelite Rule. Her main inspiration comes from Sacred Scripture, on which the Carmelite nun, day by day, is to build her interior life. The *Exhortations*, then, belong to that genre of spiritual writings, which became popular in the fifteenth century thanks to the overwhelming influence of the *devotio moderna*, which tend to be realistic, moralising, and psychological, i.e., centred on living the spiritual life in the everyday.⁵⁵ It is most probable that d’Amboise’s direct connection to the *devotio*, apart from Soreth, comes through her Belgian confessor, Matthieu de la Croix, who introduced her to Thomas à Kempis’ *Imitatio Christi* and the affective devotion to the suffering humanity of Christ. In fact, in d’Amboise’s immediate context and in connection with the *devotio moderna*, it must be remembered that the *Imitatio Christi* was one of the first devout texts to be translated into French in 1447,⁵⁶ and its intended audience were religious men and women observing the cloistered life.⁵⁷ In quite a few instances, d’Amboise’s *Exhortations* clearly resonate with ideas from the *Imitatio Christi*. In his study on the Constitutions of the first Carmelite nuns in France, Wilderink establishes such connections with the spiritual ideals of the *devotio moderna*. He identifies eighteen instances where the text of the *Exhortations* seemingly cites indirectly the *Imitatio Christi*. He is convinced that d’Amboise was familiar with this text, which was known in France as *L’Internelle Consolacion* (“The Inner Consolation”). Basing ourselves upon this working premise, this study will not limit itself to Wilderink’s eighteen connections, but will seek to indicate resonances with other authors of the wider movement of the *devotio moderna*.⁵⁸

⁵⁵ François Vandenbroucke, “Nouveaux milieux, nouveaux problèmes du XII^e au XVI^e siècle,” in *La Spiritualité du Moyen Age*, Histoire de la Spiritualité Chrétienne 2 (Paris: Aubier, 1961), 512-525.

⁵⁶ Wilderink, *Les constitutions des premières carmelites en France*, 123.

⁵⁷ Jorge Luis Bello Díaz, *Comentarios al textos de “Las exhortaciones” de la Beata Francisca d’Amboise*, unpublished manuscript in the authors’ possession, 3.

⁵⁸ See, Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Française d’Amboise,” 229-238; Wilderink, *Les constitutions des premières carmelites en France*, 178-187.

Peace, the Underlying Motif and Ideal

D’Amboise makes a few references to her tumultuous historical context of wars and tribulations,⁵⁹ as she was not alien to the fifteenth century’s own lot of “vengeance among princes, party passion in cities and states, the diligent pursuit of social hostilities at every level of the pyramid of status, the universal conviction that the social and political worlds were divided into one’s friends and one’s enemies.”⁶⁰ In her own words, “the present times are dangerous: death is everywhere.”⁶¹ Being peace her purposive antidote to this, going through the *Exhortations* one would not be mistaken in concluding that the attainment of peace, strenuously worked for, is truly the underlying motif. Firstly, in two instances she asks her community to pray for peace among princes and for peace in France and Brittany.⁶² Secondly, she recommends peace to her community interiorly and exteriorly, on the personal as well as on the communal level.⁶³ Thirdly, and most importantly, the *Exhortations* implicitly point to the attainment of peace and harmony coming from God, to whom “we should always resort, and who never fails to listen to us if we ask something for our salvation.”⁶⁴ In John Bossy’s words, “The characteristic of Christian relationship was peace, the peace which equalled friendship,”⁶⁵ perceived as “an expression of charity.”⁶⁶ Thus, it should come to no surprise that d’Amboise concluded her exhortations to the community by almost always recommending peace (*la paix*). Bossy calls

⁵⁹ See, *Exhortations*, 13, 14, 18, 22.

⁶⁰ John Bossy, *Christianity in the West: 1400-1700* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1985), 39. On the Late Medieval issues of power, calamities and warfare see: Joseph H. Lynch, *The Medieval Church: A Brief History* (London-New York: Longman, 1992), 303-335; R. N. Swanson, *Religion and Devotion in Europe, c.1215 - c.1515*, Cambridge Medieval Textbooks (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997), 235-310; John France, *The Crusades and the Expansion of Catholic Christendom, 1000-1714* (London: Routledge, 2005), 251-285.

⁶¹ *Exhortations*, 7. The “dangers” which d’Amboise speaks of refer to the tensions and wars between the King of France, Louis XI, and Burgandy and Brittany who were greatly helped by the British monarchy. For a more detailed historical account, see, Craig Taylor, “War, Propaganda, and Diplomacy in Fifteenth-Century France and England,” in *War, Government, and Power in Late Medieval France*, ed. Christopher Allmand (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 200), 70-91.; Wilderink, “Les ‘Exhortations’ de la Bienheureuse Française d’Amboise,” 230-2.

⁶² *Exhortations*, 1, 13.

⁶³ *Exhortations*, 6.

⁶⁴ *Exhortations*, 3. The same principle, this time with regards to the dangerous times, is repeated in chapter 14.

⁶⁵ Bossy, *Christianity in the West*, 59.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, 60.

this characteristic “the social miracle” which permeated Christian relations on all levels of the ecclesial and political life.

The foundations of peace and salvation for d’Amboise lie in God and not in human effort or merit. She insists that “we cannot do anything meritorious before God, if we do not observe that which we have promised to him, namely our vows,” according to the prescriptions of the Statutes and the Rule.⁶⁷ Religious observance for d’Amboise is an expression of one’s own humble, peaceful submission in obedience to God from whom salvation flows. Indeed, the very practical recommendations d’Amboise herself makes to her community are primarily meant to maintain the Rule’s prescriptions on the *custodia ordinis*. In this particular orientation of the community towards the desired ideal of peace, primacy is given to the virtue of silence which is the pledge of peace and harmony. D’Amboise echoes the spirit of the Carmelite Rule, rooted in biblical revelation, which dedicates an entire chapter on silence.⁶⁸ In d’Amboise’s view silence educates the practitioner in wisdom and in proper talk and behaviour, it forms them in compassion and favours a climate of true peace and justice.⁶⁹

Looking at her particular social and ecclesial context, one could say that d’Amboise views the religious community as an exemplary unity of peaceful and harmonious living in reparation of the calamities of the world and the Church. It is worth pointing out that the *Exhortations* start with a meditation on Jesus’ warning in Jn 16:8 with regards to the coming of the Holy Spirit. As the Paraclete, the Spirit will “convict the world in regard to sin and righteousness and condemnation.” D’Amboise dwells on sin and the condemnation of the world “primarily due to our negligence” with regards to lack of obedience and reparation, as well as curiosity regarding the faults of others.⁷⁰ Placing this statement in the wider context of the ecclesial and social life, it resonates with the concern generated by the recent trauma of the Great Western Schism (1378-1417) which had devastating effects on the Church and European society as “it meant division, hatred and conflict in what should have been the centre of unity and peace. People were alarmed that it had happened, and the more sensitive

⁶⁷ *Exhortations*, 5.

⁶⁸ “In silence and hope will be your strength.” See: *Carmelite Rule*, 21. For an indepth study on silence in the Carmelite mystical tradition see: Charlò Camilleri, “Il silenzio mistico carmelitano: Lo spirito profetico di Elia e della Vergine Maria nel Carmelo,” in *Silenzio, Polifonia di Dio: Atti del Convegno (Pontificia Università Gregoriana, 7-9 marzo 2019)*, Theologia 17, eds., Barbara Aniello and Dariusz Kowalczyk (Rome: GBP, 2020), 149-163.

⁶⁹ “Profilo storico-biografico,” in *Esortazioni*, ed. Carmelo S. Anna, 26.

⁷⁰ *Exhortations*, 1.

were upset by the fear that everyone would get used to it. It imperilled their earthly welfare and their prospects of eternal salvation.”⁷¹ The Christian people, however, knew that in the end the Saviour was Christ and not the hierarchical Church.⁷²

An Appropriate Structure to Nourish the Spiritual Life

Hence, the need for an appropriate life project leading into the path of obedience to God “into which everything is contained.”⁷³ The thrusting force of the life project presented by d’Amboise to her community starts in the context of interiority as an attitude of adherence to God through discretion, vigilance and attention, examination of conscience, meditation, and above all charity, which are repeatedly mentioned in the *Exhortations*. The *Exhortations*, in fact, echo the contemporaneous distinction made in the medieval Western moral tradition with regards to the seven deadly sins between the spirit and the flesh and, consequently, the division of sins according to whether these were in effect diseases of one or the other.⁷⁴ The heightened preoccupation to avoid those of the spirit is evident in d’Amboise’s recommendations, notwithstanding the very practical tone of her observations on communal and personal faults. If the strict enclosure envisaged for her foundations, and taken as a fourth vow alongside obedience, poverty, and chastity, kept ‘the world’ at bay from the cloisters, her admonitions kept disorder at bay from the hearts, minds, and lifestyle of her nuns “as nothing disturbs the soul, as much as worldly things.”⁷⁵ Silence, prayer, and meditation alongside work and communal charity are tools intended to preserve the witness of a prophetic community in harmful times, especially when “professed religious [were] mostly compromised and hypocritical.”⁷⁶ Considering this, d’Amboise points out that “it is very easy and rapid to make the profession; it’s a matter of uttering some words. The challenge is to put into practice all that this profession entails. It is much better not to bind oneself with such an obligation, only to do very little or nothing about it.”⁷⁷

⁷¹ Bossy, *Christianity in the West*, 3.

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ *Exhortations*, 1.

⁷⁴ Bossy, *Christianity in the West*, 35.

⁷⁵ *Exhortations*, 7.

⁷⁶ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 1.

⁷⁷ *Exhortations*, 19.

In this respect, the *Exhortations* are in line with the new ‘modern devout’ way, which encouraged reading Sacred Scriptures, meditating upon them daily, and living a deep interior life built on self-awareness, self-gift, and a communal sharing of material goods “to embody ‘piety’ in the ‘present day.’”⁷⁸ For d’Amboise, in fact, it is not “saintly times which make people holy, but holy people sanctify time.”⁷⁹ It has been shown by Wilderink that the *Exhortations* draw inspiration, amongst others, from the *Imitatio Christi*. In a more general way, d’Amboise directly refers to citations from the Sacred Scriptures and the Carmelite Rule.⁸⁰ It could be stated that her narrative, biographical and moral, falls in line with the so-called second wave of female foundations, referred to by Madelon van Luijk as the second religious women’s movement starting at the end of the fourteenth century. In this period, starting from the Netherlands, many women turned to live either in a ‘devout’ community or in a monastery and contributed to the production of devotional texts written by the nuns themselves.⁸¹

In the case and context of d’Amboise and her *Exhortations*, one must also keep in mind that generally Carmelite spiritual texts are “totally focused on the mystical process which inevitably [is] the call of every human being.”⁸² In this respect, since its early history, Carmel shares this common spirit with the masters of the *devotio moderna*. Although not anti-intellectual like the devouts, Carmelites did not engage primarily in speculative ratiocination; rather, it was *lectio divina*, meditation, and constant prayer, alongside a very deep experience of Christ present in the Eucharist that brought Carmelites to the discovery of the logic of the mystical process. The literary production of both friars and nuns centred mainly on the Scriptures and on the transformation of the human

⁷⁸ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 1.

⁷⁹ *Exhortations*, 5.

⁸⁰ Not counting indirect references, there are twenty-six direct references to Scripture and thirteen direct references to the Carmelite Rule.

⁸¹ See the seminal study of Madelon van Luijk, *Bruiden van Christus: De tweede religieuze vrouwenbeweging in Leiden en Zwolle, 1380-1580* (Zutphen: Walburg Pers, 2004). This study takes the foundations in Lieden and Zwolle after 1380, as exemplars. Amongst others, van Luijk does not only point to the production of devotional texts written by the sisters themselves, but discusses also the role of the prioress, the procuratrix, the chaplain, the devotional exercises, the chapter of faults, and works or activities done by the nuns. These are all elements treated somehow in detail by d’Amboise in her *Exhortations*.

⁸² Hein Blommestijn, “Il primo periodo della mistica nel Carmelo,” in *Mistica e mistica carmelitana*, Collana Studi Carmelitani, ed. Luigi Borriello (Città del Vaticano: LEV, 2002), 67.

being in Divine Love who is encountered in Scriptures and in the eucharistic sacrament.⁸³

In both Carmel and the *devotio moderna*, it is particularly in the attentive reading of God’s Law, Sacred Scripture, that the soul awakens in joyful blessedness to God living in her by grace. In Brandsma’s words, significant progression in the spiritual life, then, means allowing oneself to be “carried away beyond our strict obligations by the pure love and joy which is the cause of our election. Prayer is not an oasis in the desert of life: it is our life. During the hours of meditation, we prepare the food which maintains it throughout the day’s work and renders our prayer continuous.”⁸⁴ Likewise, for Geert Groote and his devout disciples, contemplation abandoned its intellectual character and identified itself with perfection of charity through spiritual poverty.⁸⁵ Indeed, one can safely hold that the text of the *Exhortations* reflects the common elements of the devout experience. In his study on the Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life, John van Engen outlines five “life-passages” that marked the spiritual project of the *devotio moderna* since its inception, namely, (i) conversion, (ii) interiority, (iii) self-examination, (iv) community life, and (v) Gospel meditation.⁸⁶ What follows is a reading of the *Exhortations* within the framework of these “life-passages” showing that, similar to the manuscript production of the devouts, the *Exhortations* were intended as a formative pedagogical tool to live a life of piety, to “nourish the spirit and profit the house”⁸⁷ in the sense of protecting the monastic enclosure from a slack lifestyle.

Conversion

The *devotio moderna* movement knows its origins to a story of conversion, that of Groote who, as he writes in one of his letters, found the ecclesiastical career “more unclean than he had words for,”⁸⁸ and resolved to make a ‘turn.’⁸⁹ Like Charles Caspers, Rijcklof Hofman suggests that the root cause of Groote’s conversion was his fear of appearing before God in an unworthy manner. In Hofman’s words, Groote concluded that “the only proper relation between a human being and God was an attitude of utmost sincerity and honesty, that

⁸³ See *ibid.*, 67-68.

⁸⁴ Brandsma, “The Spirituality of the Carmelites,” 188.

⁸⁵ Vandenbroucke, *Storia della spiritualità*, 343.

⁸⁶ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 2.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, 6.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*, 12.

⁸⁹ Groote, *Epistola 12*, as quoted in Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 12.

the prime condition for such a relationship was man's full and unconditional commitment to serve God, and that no compromise was possible [...] each individual believer should behave sincerely in his personal relationship with God.⁹⁰ This same sentiment runs through his disciples, the authors of the *devotio moderna*, as the leitmotif and the start of a new life seen as a turning away from family, career, and the world towards God. Kempis' Lenten prayer resounds along the same line of conversion as the continuous turning of the heart to God, "I to my Beloved; and His turning is towards me."⁹¹ The movement of conversion starts by recognising one's own fragility,⁹² and the longings of the soul seeking God.⁹³

It is significant that the *Exhortations* of similarly open with a call to conversion, a call to turn from the spirit of the world upon recognising its sinfulness. This recognition is immediately transformed by d'Amboise in an examen of conscience on negligence in obedience to God and in reparation for the evil committed by ourselves to instead being curious on the faults of others.⁹⁴ This goes against the resolution to totally give oneself to God in the Christian life through the observance of the commandments and, specifically in religious life, through the profession of the vows.⁹⁵ Instead, in line with the *devotio's* way of keeping alive the "memorials of departed companions as a way to kindle and rekindle their own zeal and purpose,"⁹⁶ the *Exhortations* state that one should "imitate the elder sisters with piety and charity,"⁹⁷ and "think and examine the lives of the saints to advance in obedience."⁹⁸ D'Amboise warns her nuns of the danger of turning back to the world through disordered attachments, taking back that which was offered to God freely.⁹⁹ She exhorts her nuns "not to think of the world, but

⁹⁰ Rijcklof Hofman, "Geert Groote's Choice of a Religious Life Without Vows," in *Inwardness, Individualization, and Religious Agency in the Late Medieval Low Countries*, Medieval Church Studies Series 43, eds., Rijcklof Hofman et al., (Turnhout: Brepols, 2020), 54.

⁹¹ Thomas à Kempis, *The Acceptable Time: Daily Readings for Lent*, ed. John J. Burke (New York: Paulist, n.d.), 37.

⁹² Thomae a Kempis, ven., *Opera Omnia: Volumen Primum*, ed. Franciscus Xav. Kraus (Augustae Treverorum [Trier]: Ed. Groppe, 1868), 365-374.

⁹³ Kempis, *Opera Omnia: Volumen Primum*, 3-7; Thomas a Kempis, *The Soliloquy of the Soul and the Garden of Roses*, trans. W. B. Flower (London: Joseph Masters, 1853), 1-10.

⁹⁴ 94. *Exhortations*, 1.

⁹⁵ *Exhortations*, 5, 10, 16.

⁹⁶ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 6.

⁹⁷ *Exhortations*, 17.

⁹⁸ *Exhortations*, 10.

⁹⁹ "You are here out of your own will." *Exhortations*, 16.

think only of God.”¹⁰⁰ In order to keep steadfast in turning towards God, “one must always keep sight of the goal of our salvation.”¹⁰¹ Ultimately, she argues in the *Exhortations*:

We have joined the religious life to flee from the world and work for our salvation, for this we must be humble as we are weak, we easily fall, when one knows her own faults, she is disquieted against herself and is displeased with herself for falling, you must then renounce your own will and accept that you are directed by another, a community knows novices’ faults better than one person.¹⁰²

Conversion, therefore, is a matter of trustfully turning to God in prayer¹⁰³ as one is aware of one’s own fragility, “acknowledging your sins,”¹⁰⁴ allowing oneself to be led in the ways of God through a mentor,¹⁰⁵ and supported by the community of faith. Ultimately, turning to God is turning towards the other, avoiding prideful self-absorption, in humble obedience, vigilance on oneself, and the practice of the virtues, in order to be attached to God and not to oneself or to one’s possessions.¹⁰⁶ “Conscientious persons,” she warns must humbly, “remain in the fear of God.”¹⁰⁷ D’Amboise speaks of this dynamic in terms of mortification and overcoming oneself through attentive discretion:

One must mortify oneself and do battle against oneself in order not be won over by temptation, when some passion arises in you, you must stop it as the enemy can use other means to make us fall into sin; to overcome this, be patient and benevolent, full of good will, make sure that your devotion grows evermore, be of the right intention, above all use discretion keeping to the straight [and narrow] path.¹⁰⁸

¹⁰⁰ *Exhortations*, 10.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰² *Exhortations*, 22.

¹⁰³ Jean Gerson popularised Hugh of St Victor’s understanding of prayer, in *De modo orandi*, as an elevation of the mind, movement of *conversio* tempered by humility and piety, supported by faith, hope and charity. See, Daniel B. Hobbins, “Gerson on Lay Devotion,” in *A Companion to Jean Gerson*, ed. Brian Patrick McGuire, (Leiden: Brill, 2011), 46. Also, John Soreth, influenced by the Victorine School of Paris, directly cites Hugh of St Victor on meditative prayer. See, Ioanne Soreth, “De silentio,” in *Expositio paraenetica in regulam carmelitarum* 17 (Paris: Ioseph Cottureau, 1625), 205-208; Grosso, *Il B. Jean Soreth (1394-1471)*, 175-176, 184-185.

¹⁰⁴ *Exhortations*, 14.

¹⁰⁵ Similar provision may be found in: Soreth “De honorando priorem ad fratres exhortatio,” 19:1, in *Expositio*, 212-214.

¹⁰⁶ *Exhortations*, 22.

¹⁰⁷ *Exhortations*, 14.

¹⁰⁸ *Exhortations*, 18.

Suffering temptations, slander, calumny and discord should not serve as excuses to allow ourselves to cave in, turning us toward ourselves,¹⁰⁹ but thrust us in the practice of kindness bearing any adversity that might come on the way, asking the Lord to grant us patience.¹¹⁰

Interiority or Devotion

The above counsels given by d'Amboise echo, almost word for word, Book Two of the *Imitatio Christi* on the interior life. Kempis explains that the end of a converted life is to construct the interior person and the making of a person at peace, bringing peace to others.¹¹¹ Conversion is primarily a turning within. Kempis' starting point is Jesus' words, "The kingdom of God is within you, says the Lord" (cf. Lk 17:20-21).¹¹² The *Exhortations* echo this understanding through the repetitive invitation to convert or return (*aller*) to God, cultivating love of God and neighbour through inner and outer silence, "Look that you do not offend God or [your sisters in] religion, you must return [convert, *aller*] to God, cultivate and preserve charity, without it our works aren't welcomed."¹¹³

Recollection and interiority are preserved in practice through avoidance of idle talk, laziness and being fidgety or agitated. While giving practical norms and warnings,¹¹⁴ d'Amboise reminds the nuns that "our state demands that we do not move from our cells, to read, meditate, pray, write, do a good deed, rest in silence, attend to our own [inner] state, participate in community acts, be humble, and bear the others' faults."¹¹⁵ Also, echoing Groote's admonishment against murmuring, she warns, "Our worse sins come from speaking too much, for which there is not much peace and joy, useless [trivial] words are to be avoided, murmuring is worse, slander worse still, and calumny and lying are the worst, such discord comes from speaking too much."¹¹⁶

¹⁰⁹ *Exhortations*, 13. A sure sign of giving in to self-absorption, for d'Amboise, is idle talk. See: chapter 11.

¹¹⁰ *Exhortations*, 13.

¹¹¹ Thomas à Kempis, *Imitatio Christi*, II, 1-4. See also, Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 80.

¹¹² Kempis, *Imitatio Christi*, II, 1.

¹¹³ *Exhortations*, 18.

¹¹⁴ Especially in chapters 17-19 where the *Exhortations* focus on rules for proper behaviour, avoidance of particular faults, and the exercise of virtues.

¹¹⁵ *Exhortations*, 17.

¹¹⁶ *Exhortations*, 11. On murmuring see also Geert Groote, "Letter [62]: On Patience and the Imitation of Christ," in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 89.

In the *Exhortations*, as in the perspective of the *devotio*, reading, meditating, and writing aim at reshaping human interiority, through interior examination and exterior example.¹¹⁷ The devout aimed at cultivating interiority through self-examination, self-discipline, and self-care,¹¹⁸ which d’Amboise gathers in words like vigilance, diligence, and discretion, “Be vigilant, remain in the state that you would want to be in at the moment of your death, be submissive and humble to the Lord our master, you must be very attentive and considerate, and be diligent in fulfilling your master’s will.”¹¹⁹ Also, “we must take good care of our habit as its exterior state reveals our inner love that we conserve for it and for inner purity; it is not the habit that will save us, but charity and the observance of our state.”¹²⁰ Clearly latching on to Jesus’ words in Mt 12:34, the notion of exteriority as a mirror of one’s interior life is echoed also in d’Amboise’s observation on idle talk, “Vain words demonstrate a vain conscience, such is her soul as are her words for the mouth speaks from the depths of the heart.”¹²¹ Such vain words are perilous to the spiritual life as they break the bond of charity, revealing a divisive heart (as opposed to a wholehearted dedication to God) which creates division within the community.¹²² Also, for the sake of charity, one is encouraged to “not demonstrate inward impatience by outer gestures or words.”¹²³

Although in a different setting, d’Amboise’s prescriptions on interiority run parallel to the devout’s way of interiority or *Innigheid* (turning inward). This turning inward which circumscribed for the devout “a social and religious position awkwardly poised between church and society, religious community and social kin,” takes a particular shape in the cloister’s setting as envisaged by d’Amboise. One of the seven prescripts in chapter 19 decrees that “it is rigorously prohibited to divulge information about the community or persons to people on the outside, you mustn’t break the confidentiality of community chapter with those who have not participated in it, in such faults, sister is severely punished.”¹²⁴

¹¹⁷ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 267. D’Amboise refers to discretion against avidness in devotions and in writing as without discernment these might also defeat their purpose, “There are some sisters who worry for writing notes, prayers, images, or rosaries, you must bring all this to the prioress and ask her permission for all of this, the prioress will then dispose of these as she pleases, obey humbly.” *Exhortations*, 21.

¹¹⁸ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 6.

¹¹⁹ *Exhortations*, 22.

¹²⁰ *Exhortations*, 15.

¹²¹ *Exhortations*, 19.

¹²² *Exhortations*, 19.

¹²³ *Exhortations*, 14.

¹²⁴ *Exhortations*, 19.

The delimitation of the cloister, as a space for an ‘inward’ community in relation to the ‘outer’ society, is hinted at in pointing out that the community’s “cloister is wide and spacious enough, and you are here out of your own will”¹²⁵ and also to the filtering of what is allowed in the monastery from the family kinship: “the prioress shall judge whether anything you receive from your family shall be given to you or someone else.”¹²⁶

In the context of the devout way which was generally critical of religious life, the *Exhortations* seem to echo Zerbolt’s and Pupper’s insistence that “higher merit accrued to religious life only by way of interiority, acting in freedom.”¹²⁷ The *Exhortations* interpret also religious vows from the perspective of cultivating the interior life. In Chapter 16, where d’Amboise dwells particularly on the vows, she speaks in terms of being observant “in the spirit of the reform of the Order.”¹²⁸ With regards to poverty, from exterior frugality, one educates the heart in being free from the entanglements of one’s own will, “Do not be attached to anything temporal, you are to be provided with everything you need, not according to your will, however, but according to the prioress’s assessment.”¹²⁹ More explicitly, d’Amboise points out that “this vow means also renouncing from your will.”¹³⁰ With regards to chastity, the *Exhortations* speak in terms of the custody of the heart, indicating again the predilection of interiority, in not allowing anything exterior to take hold of one’s own constant perseverance in God’s service. In line with the medieval understanding of the relationship between chastity and social relations, where “unchastity [was regarded] as a social offence, and uncharity as a type of the unclean,”¹³¹ d’Amboise connects chastity with empathy for the poor and obedience:

Chastity must be guarded well, this merit is truly equal to that of the martyrs and virgins, you must not fear or regret anything which the enemy or the world might do or say, be strong and constant in your holy battle, be glad and entrust yourselves to God your spouse who is always with those who find themselves in tribulations, as we are always inclined towards our sensuality, favour those who

¹²⁵ *Exhortations*, 16.

¹²⁶ *Exhortations*, 16.

¹²⁷ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 314.

¹²⁸ *Exhortations*, 16.

¹²⁹ *Exhortations*, 16. Groote counseled for temperance and frugality, not strict austerity in order not starve the spirit, nor to take too much of the body. See, Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 6.

¹³⁰ *Exhortations*, 16.

¹³¹ Bossy, *Christianity in the West*, 37.

beg alms for the love of God, let go of reason, obey another’s will for the love of God and for your salvation.¹³²

Echoing Meister Eckhart (c.1260-c.1328), Beatrice of Nazareth’s *Seven Manners of Loving* (c.1250), and Liesbeth van Delft (d. 1423), the *Exhortations* present obedience in terms of the devout ideal of leaving behind all the why’s.¹³³ “Forget yourself and your will,” advises d’Amboise, “it is more important to obey than to finish that which you’ve started, we are in a battleground and the enemy suggests disruptive thoughts to us such as ‘Why are they giving me too much work?’ ‘Why don’t they make someone else do it?’; leave behind all your why’s and trust in the prioress.”¹³⁴ D’Amboise qualifies these statements by showing that true obedience is an interior humble act or disposition of listening. “It is not a question of sentiments, believing oneself to be wiser than those who are in charge, as one is not supposed to obey just anyone; to obey, one must have humility.” Obedience in this way gives space to the other to manifest her opinion according to one’s own conscience, in charity:

Help one another in the path of salvation, there is more joy in listening in silence than winning and overturning another by replying.¹³⁵

We must have great love and affection for that which must be done and avoided [...] when you are asked of your opinion, respond according to your conscience, do not avoid to tell the truth out of fear or complacency.¹³⁶

Above all, observe that which you have promised to the Lord, may he give us the grace to follow him in humility, chastity, poverty of spirit, obedience, and every other virtue.¹³⁷

These provisions are meant to help the individual and the community to examine and evaluate themselves. Ultimately, these fit into the ideal type of the devout. As Zerbolt teaches in *De reformatione*, those who turn to the new way must “be able to rule and regulate themselves, judging themselves. Reading,

¹³² *Exhortations*, 16.

¹³³ See, Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 77; Jos Huls, *The Minne-Journey: Beatrice of Nazareth’s ‘Seven Ways of Minne’, Mystical Process and Mystagogical Implications*, Fiery Arrow Series (Leuven: Peeters, 2013), 15.

¹³⁴ *Exhortations*, 16.

¹³⁵ *Exhortations*, 14.

¹³⁶ *Exhortations*, 17.

¹³⁷ *Exhortations*, 17.

admonishing and spiritual guidance aimed at cultivating the inner life, self-knowledge, and self-care.”¹³⁸

Furthermore, d’Amboise does not dismiss the inevitability of human suffering as an integral part of life. In the *Exhortations* she refers to the presence of the sick within the community, promoting compassion and discretion in caring for them to charitably alleviate their pain. However, her discussion on suffering echoes again that of the *Imitatio Christi*:

Now, all our peace in this miserable life is found in humbly enduring suffering rather than in being free from it. He who knows best how to suffer will enjoy the greater peace, because he is the conqueror of himself, the master of the world, a friend of Christ, and an heir of heaven.¹³⁹

From a spiritual perspective, suffering is conducive to interiority as an opportunity to make peace with the transitoriness and impermanence of life, thrusting the devout to adhere to that which is essential and eternal. D’Amboise refers to various occasions and circumstances which might cause suffering either interiorly or exteriorly, as shown in these sections of the *Exhortations*:

If the Lord permits that we suffer, it’s because he loves us. It is better to suffer in this world than in the next; the cross of Christ is the only path by which we can go to heaven. Humility, suffering [are occasions] to serve and love God better. Tame your natural inclinations, win over yourself, know how much a word or gesture can hurt, grow in virtue, especially humility.¹⁴⁰

Leave behind any questioning, think of Our Lord’s so grand and decisive obedience who for our salvation chose to suffer a most painful and ignominious death that there could ever be, place yourself at the foot of the cross and there rest peacefully.¹⁴¹

Do not offend yourself too easily for some word or gesture, if any difference is noted speak about it to bring about peace, keep yourself in a good state.¹⁴²

¹³⁸ Engen, *Sisters and Brothers of the Common Life*, 294.

¹³⁹ Kempis, *Imitatio Christi*, II, 3.

¹⁴⁰ *Exhortations*, 8.

¹⁴¹ *Exhortations*, 16. Chapter 13 then is totally dedicated to the carrying of the Cross with Christ. In *On Patience and the Imitation of Christ*, Groote lists three reasons why a devout soul should always keep in mind the cross of Christ. By and large these are echoed in d’Amboise’s text. Firstly, “out of loving desire to honor and imitate Christ Jesus and be configured to him,” secondly, “out of love for divine fruits, merits and rewards that so richly flow from trials and tribulations,” and thirdly, “out of love and fervor to satisfy divine justice, which we so gravely offend in many ways.” Groote “Letter [62]: On Patience and the Imitation of Christ,” in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 85.

¹⁴² *Exhortations*, 18.

Ultimately, suffering lived in the context of an interior life always provides an occasion to mature in humility, to better serve God and others in self-giving, to be one with the crucified Christ, and grow in the knowledge of self.

Self-Examination

Jesus’ admonition in the *Imitatio Christi* to the priest coming near the house of God and the altar is to “carefully examine your conscience.”¹⁴³ This exercise, so dear to the devout, is to be found in most of the writings of the *devotio moderna*. It is an exercise so indispensable to grow in self-knowledge. D’Amboise greatly exhorts her nuns to examine themselves regularly, if not constantly, “We’ve all come here [to the cloister] for our salvation, we must pay close attention to the manner in which we are tempted, and from where they [temptations] proceed; in fact, many do not know how to be stable in one place, these have a fickle soul.”¹⁴⁴ The sole purpose of joining the cloister is to examine and reform oneself in order to be able to persevere in the service of God. D’Amboise exhorts her nuns several times on this important motif in the spiritual life. In chapter 20, similarly to Groot’s *Letter 29* although less dramatically, she admonishes:

Pay attention to your conscience, be vigilant, do not trust too much in your religious habit and in the fact that you are here, temptation is everywhere,¹⁴⁵ be attentive particularly of small, subtle animosities and disgusts against one another, be content in your own vocation, pray to God that he might give us the grace of acting well, and that his will be done in us;

flee laziness and use your time well, carry yourself for the service of God to resist temptations;

the enemy will tempt us not with grave sins, such as avarice, but with resentment for some word said in haste and subtle suspicions towards someone, be vigilant and don’t give space to these things.¹⁴⁶

Constantly, she warns – almost pleads with – her nuns to “be vigilant over one’s passions through reason; to be careful of one’s words which are a source of much waste of time; to regulate one’s will through reason; to mortify one’s

¹⁴³ Kempis, *Imitatio Christi*, VII, 1

¹⁴⁴ *Exhortations*, 20.

¹⁴⁵ See, Kempis, *Imitatio Christi*, III, 35.2

¹⁴⁶ *Exhortations*, 20.

affections, passions, and will,”¹⁴⁷ and, ultimately, to be attached to God and not to creatures, to live in fraternal charity.¹⁴⁸

D’Amboise knows the perils of living a deep interior spiritual life, of facing constantly one’s inner demons or evil destructive thoughts that might lead to resentment, *acedia*, or laziness.¹⁴⁹ Hence, the *Exhortations* provide the means to examine and protect oneself from temptations. First, she points out that self-examination is a tool to grow in virtue¹⁵⁰ and, hence, to prevent oneself from being trapped in scrupulosity. Throughout the text, one notices the constant reminder to be vigilant, to show discretion in food, clothing, and devotion, to preserve holy thoughts, to cherish a well-regulated heart, and to keep oneself in a good state.¹⁵¹ In the spirit of the Carmelite Rule, d’Amboise also speaks of work as a spiritual exercise that will also help her nuns in the process of self-examination, “Work and service to God amount to the same degree of importance in religious life as is the observance of the regular life.”¹⁵² To this, she also adds avoiding excessive sensitivity which is the enemy of a healthy life in common.

Through fraternal love, gratefulness to God and to the community proves to be a good antidote to overcome such dangers, “Do not offend yourself too easily for some word or gesture, if any difference is noted speak about it to bring about peace, do not be ungrateful towards God, consider the state you were in before you joined the Order and the state you are in now, resist your natural evil inclinations.”¹⁵³ Most importantly, self-examination as conducive to know one’s true self is fundamental for vocational discernment, “A novice must know herself and her faults; she must see whether she wants to submit herself [to community life], some advance better alone than in community, no one knows us reasonably better than ourselves.”¹⁵⁴

¹⁴⁷ *Exhortations*, 9.

¹⁴⁸ See, *Exhortations*, 9, 15, 21.

¹⁴⁹ *Exhortations*, 1, 7.

¹⁵⁰ *Exhortations*, 12.

¹⁵¹ See, *Exhortations*, 3, 4, 7, 10, 13, 14, 15.

¹⁵² *Exhortations*, 12. Zerbolt advises the devout to do “manual and corporeal labor” and to persevere in the exercises of the spiritual path. See: Gerard Zerbolt of Zutphen, “The Spiritual Ascents,” in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 309.

¹⁵³ *Exhortations*, 18. The same advice, in terms of loving God and neighbour, is found in Zerbolt’s *Spiritual Ascents* to battle tedium. Zerbolt, “The Spiritual Ascents,” in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 303.

¹⁵⁴ *Exhortations*, 22.

Community Life

Knowledge of self through self-examination is not only salutary for the individual progress in the spiritual life, but also for a decent life in community. The *Exhortations* seem to indicate that all troubles and tensions in community life originate in lack of self-knowledge. Hence, the need for having the right intention, the cultivation of interior purity of heart, and to act in everything for God’s love.¹⁵⁵

Reminding the community that “we are all sisters with the same habit and the same profession,”¹⁵⁶ the *Exhortations* call for mutual respect, the show of sweetness and love with one another, and to be patient especially with the sick.¹⁵⁷ D’Amboise cautions her nuns that “the less some know about themselves, the more they seek to know about others,”¹⁵⁸ noting that they become, out of curiosity, more concerned with judging the faults of others than their own.¹⁵⁹ D’Amboise does not tire from repeatedly warning that there exists in the community the danger of vainglory – expressed in vain words – which should be cured through the antidote of humility, empathy and charity.¹⁶⁰ The life-structure of the community should provide for a safe space where evaluations of life, common behaviour and, if need be, fraternal corrections could be pointed out in the weekly chapter “to keep in line with our conscience [...] vigilant, and attentive of ourselves.”¹⁶¹ Echoing the Gospel (cf. Mt 18-15:20) and the Carmelite Rule (n. 15), d’Amboise shows that in fraternal correction, when exercised in true humility, the care for the spiritual good of the other is tantamount to conversion, care, and charity.¹⁶² On the other hand one should humbly accept correction and not trust one’s own opinion of self.¹⁶³ Also echoing the Apostle’s admonition in Eph. 6:1-4, d’Amboise advises not to importune the other with corrections, but if necessary to do so gently. It is better to resolve to prayer, keeping in mind that ultimately one has to answer for oneself for one’s own faults.¹⁶⁴ Inquiring about

¹⁵⁵ *Exhortations*, 17.

¹⁵⁶ *Exhortations*, 2.

¹⁵⁷ *Exhortations*, 2.

¹⁵⁸ *Exhortations*, 1.

¹⁵⁹ *Exhortations*, 6

¹⁶⁰ See, *Exhortations*, 2, 8, 10, 11, 13, 14, 22

¹⁶¹ *Exhortations*, 14, 20.

¹⁶² See, *Exhortations*, 6, 11, 14

¹⁶³ *Exhortations*, 6.

¹⁶⁴ *Exhortations*, 6.

the faults of others shows that one has a disordinate soul. So, one should always keep discretion and secrecy on the faults of others.¹⁶⁵

Another aspect in regulating the welfare of the community and the *custodia ordinis* within it deals with provisions on practicalities concerning life in common. One finds these provisions coming from monastic and religious *milieux*, including the *devotio moderna* movement. One such text is *A Way of Life for Sisters* by Salome Sticken.¹⁶⁶ The *Exhortations*, in fact, give provisions to preserve equality and equity on serving in the refectory, behaviour in choir, relations between the elder and the younger members, converse and chorist sisters, dealing with novices,¹⁶⁷ and the keeping of the community vestiary (linens, habits, mantles, and such).¹⁶⁸ Other provisions include counsels on the recommended time for which the prioress should hold office.¹⁶⁹ Others speak of the harm of benefices, and even rebukes a disordered lifestyle which harms the individual and the community alike.¹⁷⁰ Though there is space for differences in community, even on the level of hierarchical structure, d'Amboise stresses that "there is one and the same Rule for everyone."¹⁷¹ In accordance with the spirit of the Carmelite Rule, the prioress' role is to guarantee order within the community. D'Amboise reminds the community that one joins religious life "for the love of God alone" in a state of life where "we have given ourselves to the will of another; obedience is the way that is taught to us by the Lord himself."¹⁷²

¹⁶⁵ See, *Exhortations*, 10, 11.

¹⁶⁶ Salome Sticken, "A Way of Life for Sisters," in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 176-186.

¹⁶⁷ In chapter 22, the *Exhortations* bring forward the case of novices coming from noble families, and having also family members in the community itself: "Community must see that novices are meek, manageable, humble, and whether they can endure being corrected for their faults, disregard the honours and family from which novice might come from; take also into consideration whether she has some family members in the community, if they are not sufficiently mortified, they will not handle seeing and enduring their relative being corrected, and will be scandalised, disturbance and rupture will ensue, rest assured that any fault must be punished."

¹⁶⁸ *Exhortations*, 3, 11, 15, 16, 20, 21, 22.

¹⁶⁹ *Exhortations*, 8.

¹⁷⁰ *Exhortations*, 20, 21.

¹⁷¹ *Exhortations*, 22.

¹⁷² *Exhortations*, 1.

Gospel Meditation

Referring to the admonition of Christ in Mt 18:6, d’Amboise exhorts her community to “not scandalize each other.”¹⁷³ One would not be mistaken to state that the *Exhortations* are, in fact, born out of her deepest concern to preserve an evangelical lifestyle within the community, which is after all the ideal of any Christian group but most especially of the Carmelite community whose ideal, as expressed in the Rule, is to “live in allegiance to Jesus Christ” and “be unswerving in the service of the Master” with purity of heart and stout conscience.¹⁷⁴ Groote advises his disciples that for the devout “the root of all your study and the mirror of life is the Gospel of Christ because there is found the life of Christ.”¹⁷⁵ Speaking to her community d’Amboise calls on her sisters “see that in everything you meditate bring out profit from”¹⁷⁶ being conformed to Christ, especially in the mystery of his passion through fidelity to one’s Christian and religious vocation according to the spirit of the reform of the Order.¹⁷⁷ Evidently, the ideal put forward by d’Amboise resonates also with that promoted by Soreth, himself a Master in the Sacred Page, whose sermons and lectures on Sacred Scripture, especially on the Pauline Epistles, indicate that the decisive themes upon which he built the reform of the Order are rooted in the Scriptures.¹⁷⁸ Also, in his *Expositio paraenetica in regulam carmelitarum*, the Prior General, dwelling on the precept “to meditate day and night on the Law of the Lord,”¹⁷⁹ shows that there is no prayer which is more valuable spiritually than the Lord’s Prayer which proceeds from the mouth of Truth itself and therefore it should be more meditated than vocally prayed.¹⁸⁰

Undoubtedly, the *Exhortations* are the fruit of d’Amboise’s constant meditation on the life of Christ in light of the Gospels. Her focus is typical of the devout manner of emphasising the example and virtues that are set by Christ,

¹⁷³ *Exhortations*, 13.

¹⁷⁴ *Carmelite Rule*, 2.

¹⁷⁵ Geert Groote, “Resolutions and Intentions, But Not Vows,” in *Devotio Moderna*, trans. John van Engen, 70.

¹⁷⁶ *Exhortations*, 12, 18.

¹⁷⁷ *Exhortations*, 16, 20.

¹⁷⁸ Grosso, *Il B. Jean Soreth (1394-1471)*, 154-155. Unfortunately, the correspondence with d’Amboise is lost, so one cannot see to what extent both figures influenced each other. See, Grosso, *Il B. Jean Soreth (1394-1471)*, 159.

¹⁷⁹ *Carmelite Rule*, 10.

¹⁸⁰ Soreth, “Frequentem virtutis cultum et orationis exercitium commendat,” 8:2, in *Expositio*, 133-5.

especially in his passion. Meditation on the Gospel aims at strengthening one in the path of discipleship as follower of Christ. D'Amboise tells her religious:

You must always carry the cross gladly and voluntarily, carry your burden in the most calmly manner possible, generously carrying the cross with Christ accompanying him, have faith and courage in the Lord for she who is not tempted does not acquire any virtue;

As the Lord says in Mk 8:34, whoever wants to follow me must deny himself, we must accept the cross and our penances, as he did for our sake;

Do not carry the cross as Simeon the Cyrene did in Lk 23:26 who did not choose to carry the cross and had to carry it against his will, praise God for having called you for this service;

Above all, show love with one another, day by day work so that you win over your passions.¹⁸¹

Finally, ending her “life-passages” as they started, d'Amboise continually exhorts her religious to cultivate the spirit of silence as an important attitude to listen to God's Word in all circumstances of life.

Conclusion

As has been noted, Engen defines the five main qualities of the devout spiritual experience as “life-passages,” that is, existential channels through which the devout passes in seeking to bring about depth and authenticity in one's spiritual life. Not only do these life-passages denote growth in one's behaviour but they also point towards a paradigm shift in how one relates to oneself, one's neighbour, and God. D'Amboise embodied each one of these passages. In conversion, her turning was constantly towards God. In her interior life, she was all too aware of the limits and transiency of this world. In self-examination, she knew herself to be weak and easily falls, which is why she would emphasise with her sisters, “When one knows her own faults, she is disquieted against herself and is displeased with herself for falling.”¹⁸² Leading by example more than mere words, in community she exhorted her nuns in the way of humility and love. In the meditation of the Gospel, she hung on to Jesus Christ as her only stronghold, the provider of salvation and eternal life. In line with the devout spiritual experience, d'Amboise's outlook on life is equally personal as it is communitarian, insisting

¹⁸¹ *Exhortations*, 13.

¹⁸² *Exhortations*, 22.

on one’s self-knowledge just as much as on one’s commitment to building a community of humble and charitable disciples.

As a duchess who chose the riches of the spirit over those of the court, being in the world but not really belonging to it, d’Amboise continues to inspire those today who are faced with the challenges of worldly life while seeking to maintain an interior openness and commitment to the divine. In a world that is likewise power-hungry and ambitious for control – although power today comes from an altogether different place than in d’Amboise’s time –, with interests to defend, fears to cap, and needs to satisfy, d’Amboise’s devout experience resonates today in terms of the true (eternal) meaning of life, the fundamental choice for the good, the preferential option for the poor, emotional and spiritual intelligence as more than therapy, the ecclesial life as a synodal encounter inspired by the Word of God, and the unconditional respect for human dignity,¹⁸³ which are all somehow echoes of the spiritual life-passages outlined herein brought together in a courageous and unified life-project more than six hundred years ago.

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¹⁸³ Recently, in 2019, the *Société d’histoire d’archéologie et des arts du Pays thoursais* organised a conference entitled “Françoise d’Amboise, une féministe avant l’heure,” delivered by Philippe Chauveau, which showcased d’Amboise as a determined diplomat who was capable of making herself ‘heard’ while remaining faithful to her values.